

THE ROLE OF AUDIO-VISUAL METHOD WHILE TEACHING ENGLISH IN SCHOOLS

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***Annotation:** The development of technology, innovations are being brought up in language teaching. Nowadays, language teachers are using different audio-visual aids to facilitate the process of instruction. Along with text books, language teachers are likely to use related pictures, audio clips, videos, power point slides, images and so on in language classroom.*

***Key words:** Audio-Visual Aids, Teaching, Students' perceptions.*

Nowadays, one thing that cannot be denied is that we live in the media world, in which most of the information were provided by audio-visual input, through different technology devices. In order to make acquisitions of the language more meaningful for the students, a teacher should adopt different techniques to teach language more efficiently and more interestingly. Audio-visual aids work as powerful tools in this aspect, as far as they gave the teachers the opportunity to show the culture of the target language. All this makes students understand that the use of target language has a purpose; the real purpose of the real-communications.

It is clear that audio visual aids are important tools for teaching learning process. It helps the teacher to present the lesson effectively and students learn and retain the concepts better and for longer duration. Use of audio visual aids improves student's critical and analytical thinking.

Audio-visual method is one of methods which can be used in the classroom to teach the students of elementary school. It uses both visual and audio media, and permit the introduction of study materials. The improved access and availability of electronic and multimedia technology has enable more students to

participate in the classroom when learning process. Audio-visual makes teaching and learning effective and useful. It is the best dissemination of knowledge and information, it also play an even more important role in classrooms. Teacher may introduce and demonstrate in many media of audio-visual such as television, video, movie, projector, computer in the classroom. It will enrich their understanding and vocabulary about English and will build a creative environment in the elementary class and create a more inviting atmosphere. Based on the explanation above, the writer is interested in finding out the effects of learning method toward the English vocabulary achievement through audio (sense of hearing) and visual (sense of seeing and watching). Students often benefit from the visual/sound appeal of audio-visual materials because it tends to focus their attention on the topic. When teachers present material in various manners, such as providing students with both a summary statement and a chart on a given topic, the visual material enhances the written materials.

Teacher may demonstrate in many types of slide and movie in the classroom. It will enrich their understanding and vocabulary about the uses of language. Through recording, radio and tape, teacher can tell telecast many interesting and informative news, history and story. These will build a creative environment in elementary class children. Apart from that “an understanding of the arts-painting, sculpture, the dance, handicrafts-can readily be taught by means of television. And both radio and television are valuable media for teaching. Audio visual part of teaching method which is designed to assist in the classroom along with presentation of material (concept, knowledge, and ideas). Audio visual aid is basically admired for best in the literature, mathematics, science, shopwork and other field, both as curricular and extracurricular. In these fields, with the help of technical device, children can have understanding and replicate it. Audio visual learning will serve effective method in disseminative knowledge even in overcrowded classroom. Without this technical device, poorly teacher prepared cannot hold the class properly. If teachers use the help of audio visual in class such as projector, which would definitely stimulate imagination and

catch the attention of students. Teachers often give instruction heavily loaded abstract verbalisms which seem meaningless sometime. So in case, teaching should be in simple and lucid manner.

Use of audio visual material in classroom, will lead towards learning with understanding, learning by watching and learning as fun not as burden. Teachers should know which things of it are relevant and which are irrelevant, specially which how audio visual aid may contribute to an understanding of the lesson being taught. Therefore, it is essential for any teacher who wants to be successful teacher, must plan carefully and worked out in advance. In certain area of schools at elementary level, the use of audio-visual materials is essential to the dissemination of the information and the skills or technique which is being taught the children. When audio- visual material are compulsory for the teaching – learning process, then it is obvious that the teacher could be replaced for these schools by a well-trained projection , functioning equipment and well-prepared self-explanatic material, such as audio visual software materials.

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